

ENGAGING CREATIVE THINKING TECHNIQUES TO SUPPORT STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Purpose – The paper offers a conceptual model in overcoming learning barriers from several directions (theoretically and practically) and focuses on students' creativity in how they approach problem solving.

Methodology/approach - The methodology is based on "Six Thinking Hats" and it is used to support creative thinking in achieving a good collaboration between teams in an educational project.

Findings – The use of creative techniques must be done in a harmonious manner, sustained, in which the time allocated to students must be sufficient to develop their creative ideas in solving a problem.

Research limitations/implications – The diversity of educational projects has a major impact on today's society because the transfer of knowledge is no longer enough, he must supplement with projects that focus on developing students' skills and changing behaviors, values and lifestyles.

Practical implications – The primary objective of the paper is to motivate academics to invest in applied workshops for students according to the economic realities. Through these workshops are emphasizes the skills and abilities of the students, offering the chances of being selected for a good job position in the most prestigious companies in Timisoara.

Originality/value – Creative thinking develops tactics for responsibilities distribution, finding accurate resources, encourages collaboration between people, and help future workforce to comply with rules regulation. Within the paper are identified unique and creative ways of transmitting knowledge that come to overcome the barriers previously identified.

Key words: students, creative thinking, educational projects

Introduction

Diversity of educational projects restores the capacity of educational institutions to be actively and practically involved in initiatives for integration and improvement of individual learning behavior. Improvement initiatives in education and technological changes have certainly influenced the new directions in society, creating structures that have the ability to empower digitalization in industries (Diaconescu, et al., 2019). Technological changes reshape the material, human, and social dimensions and offer solutions when society is facing the biggest challenges (ex. pandemic COVID-19). During pandemic COVID-19 higher education has reorienting his strategy and force universities towards digitized education by imposing necessary measures to analyze digital techniques used, those that support education and training systems. Consequently, all these changes had a remarkable influence on the educational environment, respectively it was a beneficial road to adapt the teaching/learning methods focusing on creative techniques and innovative technologies. More precisely exists a tacit cooperative acceptance from each university that recognizes these days the importance and advantages provided by digitized education. The advantage brought by digitized education is that it disseminates timely information through various platforms and encourages students to experiment with new learning means, developing them new digital skills and competencies that are necessary for self-

development but also good employment in market work. According to the current educational situation presented above students facing multiple changing demands on their competencies, skills especially as problem solvers in projects. These demands come from the educational systems that continue practices from the 20th century, hindering the progress of the student's varied learning style or the devotion of learners as well as proper integration into the labor market. In this sense, project-based learning is a solution in preparing students for the 21st century because projects focus on learning objectives, including skills such as: critical thinking, problem solving, communication, collaboration and self-management.

The present paper highlighting the necessity in adopting a novel movement in higher education where is an urgent need to encourage students to explore creative thinking in solving problems and bring innovation in their received projects. The new generation of students is willing to absorb and integrate more creative tools into the current learning process. Exploring creative thinking at an early stage can provide graduates with relevant occupational skills in today's work communities. The next step of the research analyzes a comprehensive set of creative thinking techniques potential to stimulate students' creativity in conducting educational projects. These types of creative thinking techniques allow students to develop tactics for business thinking and solve imminent issues.

Creative thinking techniques for educational projects

Starting from the findings in the labor market, the educational system noticed a mismatch between the number of college graduates and the expectations and needs of the industry. This fact had a great impact as a result of which the educational system created a realistic link with the business environment between the career paths and the aspirations of current and future students. It is noted that academia and industry work together to develop programs that end the separation between university and market work, in a way that provides equal opportunities for all students, regardless of context and career aspirations. As example, educational programs for engineering sciences should enhance and emphasize the creative and innovative nature of engineers' work, although knowledge of mathematics and science is important and necessary, they must not have a monopoly on the necessary skills set. Engineering students enlist and enthusiastically seek out authentic and relevant engineering experiences. Training a professional engineer is a process; one that involves education, training and experience. Creative trainings in the case of engineering teams demonstrate how creative interventions through specific methods can produce the best results for the assigned projects. According to Liu, and Schonwetter, (2004) they believe that creative engineers must have the ability to explore and examine available data or information, possibly to find new solutions to solve specific engineering problems or to produce a unique product.

There are a comprehensive set of creative thinking techniques that allow students to develop skills in imminent issues and tactics as problem solvers for educational projects.

There are presented as follows:

- *Mind mapping* (known as brainstorming or spider diagrams) helps idea generation. The necessary clue behind the use in mind mapping is to take into account every idea that arises. Mind mapping provides a path of the mind that comprises a network of concepts, connected and chained together. This path transposes some visual, nonlinear representations of their ideas and relationships (Biktimirov and Nilson 2006). The advantage of this method besides “free-form” and unconstrained structure is that any opinion can be harmoniously arranged to any other. Spontaneous, free, intuitive thinking offers creative associations between ideas (Davies, 2011).
- *The Checklist* represents a standardized group of objects used to remind the main thinker of the multitude of possible variants for approaching a problem and obtaining a solution. The checklist can refer to the five senses, human needs, physical attributes. This method can also have custom checklists. The personalized approach can be used individually to refresh ideas even when are involve more factors in the game. Checklists are useful in keeping the creator of ideas active or solving problems alert to many aspects of the problem.
- *Six Thinking Hats* appeared due to the creation of Edward de Bono in 1985 and has become an easy-to-use tool through which the business environment is stimulated to approach an innovative vision. This creative tool offers different features in related stages when moments of analysis and debates around issues are needed, indicating an optimal decision. This method

has, through the creative approach, a distinct set of colored areas, a kind of creative stage of analysis of a problem, through which the initiator finally reaches an innovative decision. More precisely, this creative tool allows the change of the individual's thinking, triggering six directions of creative analysis. These directions lead to six colored areas called White Hat - Past Facts, Red Hat - Emotions provided, Black Hat - Reasoning, Yellow Hat - Logical Arguments, Green Hat - Adding New Ideas, Blue Hat - Surveillance (de Bono, 2006).

- *Lateral thinking* is a tool elaborated by Edward de Bono (1970) that describes a type of thinking that is unconventional (Butler, 2010). Lateral thinking is a skill that can be accessed by everyone and can be developed through training. De Bono encourages users to look at their situation differently and to re-analyze their problem from a much more creative perspective. Although the concept of lateral thinking has not emerged recently, the method offers a special feature by trying to separate the individual characteristics of decision makers and identifying lateral thinkers. The knowledge gained through this approach develops a better ability to understand decision makers who use heuristic rules. Lateral thinking generally makes mental connections in three ways, namely similarity, closeness or opposition. Lateral thinking seeks to find a different answer. It is not particularly desired to stagger correct steps in lateral thinking, because the correct answer is not sought. Lateral thinking uses the premise of stepping stones, looking for available stones to switch thinking elsewhere. Lateral thinking involves two categories: techniques that involve metaphor (looking for similarities and closeness); and techniques involving reversal (search for oppositions).
- *Random Word Stimulation* represents a dynamic procedure through which the practical method consists in accessing the mind of the individual's subconscious, through which other information is used, to generate new original ideas. In practice, the applied method allows the brain to make quick connections, giving it a way to adapt to this style of thinking in free form. This adaptation strengthens the connection with the subconscious mind and endows the practitioner with creativity and brings improvements to critical thinking.

Whatever the applicability of creative methods, group, or individual, these intend to improve the knowledge transfer, in so being performed innovation (Badea, et al., 2013). Creative thinking techniques allow individuals to apply strategies for identifying problems, making decisions, and finding solutions both in and out of learning class.

Currently, creativity is a vital tool for innovation in educational projects. Most innovations in technology came to life due to creativity. Technology influences creative thinking and facilitates the applicability of analytical thinking (Charyton and Merrill 2009). In the practical approaches it was observed that the set of creative thinking tools are based on the same structure repeating the same methodical models (Kohls, 2012). The great successful personalities schematically implant a strategic vision about life and business in a very rational and positive way. This planning is part of the reason why most viewers have been successful. But in their evolution many times, they encountered difficulties in how to perceive a problem from an emotional, intuitive, creative, or negative point of view. These difficulties have developed some notable shortcomings in their development of underestimating resistance to plans or the inability to make creative leaps and essential contingency plans. Due to these difficulties, the "Six Thinking Hats" method developed by de Bono (1971) came to aid focusing on an individual's creative potential.

Investigating described above techniques, we considered appropriate for creative process teaching and practice, the application of the "Six Thinking Hats" method for an educational project.

Methodology

During the last decades, learning prospects for future generations of students have experienced radical changes in many business areas. Now interdisciplinarity and globalization have transformed student communities into a uniform arena of collaboration which is expanding beyond culture and context, and where creativity becomes an important milestone in developing educational projects for students. Educational projects harness students' creativity, and subsequently, allow an examination of how creativity techniques are applied in the classroom by providing students with a set of tools to use further in their exploratory behavior. Creative curriculum has quickly become a topic of great interest in recent years due to digitalization in teaching and learning. In addition to training in creative techniques, students must have good communication skills, collaboration, information networks, feedback and reception, teamwork, and even in some cases cultural understanding. All these qualities listed and corroborated

with creative techniques helps in highlighting competencies required in implementing an educational project. Due to the usefulness of creative techniques, the authors considered the application of the "Six Thinking Hats" technique by Edward de Bono (2006) regarding the development of the creative process within a teamwork project.

The methodology used in this paper is based on "Six Thinking Hats" and it is applied to support creative thinking in achieving a good collaboration between teams in an educational project. The method is useful when issues are debates from all possible angles, and problems must be solved to select the important decision.

The basic idea behind the concept of the "Six Thinking Hats" method was that the human brain makes distinct reasonings that can be deliberately provoked. These reasonings are organized in a structured way, so that appropriate spaces are allocated through which tactics can be developed for certain problems. The method signals the problems faced by the individual but gradually find the necessary solutions to solve problems. The graduality of the six ways of thinking can be accessed, when distinct programs are created.

Table 1. Six Thinking Hats description

Six Thinking Hats	
White Hat	<i>Information gathering Data, information, facts — known and needed</i>
	The white hat thinking provides the group with information on how to approach the problem.
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the details of the problem description? • What are the implications of these details? • Are there any issues that are missing? • What is the goal pursued? • How will we get the missing information?
Red Hat	<i>Feelings, intuition and emotions</i>
	The red hat thinking encourages the group to express their feelings about the course of an action.
Affirmations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I don't think the idea suits me. • I have a good feeling for this option. • I am afraid to get involved in this approach.
Green Hat	<i>Creativity, new ideas and possibilities</i>
	The green hat thinking offers an opportunity to find new approaches and innovative solutions.
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the newest way we can do this? • What are the views on tackling the problem in the opposite direction? • What alternatives are known and have not been considered?
Yellow Hat	<i>The logical benefits of solutions. The generally accepted vision.</i>
	The yellow hat thinking allows the group to emphasize the creative ideas of a new idea or a certain decision and how feasible they are.
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the benefits of a new idea? • How this new idea can be applied?
Black Hat	<i>Expression of risks. Incompatibilities and potential difficulties.</i>
	The black hat thinking encourages the group to take into account the weaknesses of an idea or solution and to discover how to avoid or counteract them.
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the weak points of the new idea? • How to avoid weak points of the new idea?
Blue Hat	<i>Process coordination. Managing productive thinking.</i>
	The blue hat thinking allows the organization and control of the thinking process and supports the discussion to be productive.
Affirmations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All discussions have been processed. • When the solutions start to be productive.

The nature of the human being is to react to instincts, some of them adopt a positive approach to problem solving, while others try to solve problems more critically. The two approaches to obtaining decisions are indispensable, even if both are exposed. "Six thinking hats" highlight important, triggering and edifying aspects from both points of view. Obtaining the triggering and edifying aspects are analyzed

from a technical point of view after they have forced the initiator to think in six different situations. Using this technique, creating different scenarios we can get the best possible solutions to any problem.

This method avoids those discussions in meetings where facts and opinions overlap in a disorderly way, without reaching a concrete conclusion. The "Six Thinking Hats" indicate first problems about an idea/product/service the thinker may come up with, and provide solutions which are analyzed from several perspectives as:

- Information gathering "**white**",
- Feelings, intuition and emotions "**red**",
- Creativity, new ideas and possibilities "**green**",
- Benefits and feasibility "**yellow**",
- Caution, criticism and assessing risks "**black**",
- Process control "**blue**".

The methodology is presented in seven steps, when putting the technique into practice, as follows:

Step 1

In this step, the session is started by exposing the operating principles of the "Six thinking hats". The method works when a target group/person is facing a specific problem. The method offers a different perspective on approaching problems and helps those who want to change thinking patterns in solving a problem. In the first stage, a trainer/moderator/leader is established to guide the group towards each scenario. In this step, the trainer establishes together with the group what problem is to be solved, in this way the sequence of hats will be clearly known. The trainer explains each colored hat and what purpose they serve. The sketch of the method must be print out, namely the colored hats, that are each attached to a separate sheet of paper where each group will write down their arguments in the assigned scenario. The materials must be distributed among participants that attend the meeting.

Step 2

Having known the procedure for carrying out the method in step one, we can move on to step two. Step two begins when the problem identified in step one went through a factual information overview. In step two the problem that needs to be solved will be assigned to a specific function of thinking, namely the white hat. Although an objective assessment of the problem is needed through facts, figures, information, the group must not offer any opinion, interpretation, criticism, or emotion.

In step two the Information gathering, white hat, must be performed. Information gathering of the problem is performed within the group. In this step, the white hat group is noticed. If the group needs guidance, the instructor can provide the group with more key information about the problem in question but only after the group presents the known data about the problem. After the statement of facts, the trainer encourages the whole group to note what emotional states (red hat) the known information causes, following that in step three to explore more views and reactions to the problem analyzed.

Step 3

After gathering information, in step three the trainer starts the in-depth discussions to collect the opinions and reactions to the problem announced in step two. In this stage the group adds the most important constraints of the problem, referring to the factual information collected of white hat. In step three, the characteristics of the red hat are applied by bringing to the surface the emotions related to the central problem. In-depth discussions within the group start with the red hat. The instructor must have some control over the mentality of the red hat because this step requires a high emotional coefficient of thinking. The group assigned to the red hat has the task to present those intuitive activities or to express the direction of the actions to treat the problem according to the received vibrations. The advantage of the red hat is that it allows the emotional expression of individuals without the need for a rational explanation.

Step 4

Step four begins only when the discussions in step three are worn-out. After the factual information and the direction of the actions for treating the problem are presented, depending on the received vibrations,

creativity can be started. Thus, in step four, the trainer assigns the green hat within the group through which innovative solutions are nuanced.

Having already known the data about the problem as well as the specific situations of the problem, the support brought by integrating creative thoughts allows obtaining a positive scenario. In this step, the inventive abilities of the group are fully exploited. Green hat focuses all creative thoughts through which individuals gain creative support when they want to change, remedy, or accept given problems.

Step 5

Despite its apparent simplicity, the method allows extraordinary results, especially when it comes to a group discussion. In this step, it happens that there is more concern for defending the point of view in a discussion, but the method has the ability to combine group thinking to find the best creative solution.

In this step, the instructor has the task to discover the set of ideas resulting from the interaction with the group and to use the outline of the printed method for the yellow hat and the black hat. At this stage the group is guided to address 2 states: an optimistic state yellow hat and a pessimistic state black hat in solving the problem. The yellow hat task allows the group to evaluate with optimism the approached problem. This state allows the cumulation of all the opportunities and advantages from the analyzed situation. Although the gravity of the situation can be harsh, the mentality of this state offers those advantageous characteristics, bringing a positivism note in the analysis of the problem. The yellow hat runs after attracting all the harmonious actions, offering optimistic variants even when the arguments become unbearably harsh. Contrary to the thinking pattern of the yellow hat is the black hat. The pattern of the black hat works in a negative way. In this state, the group is forced to express its criticism, the pessimism that results from the analysis of the given problem. The mentality of the black hat can be a margin of protection to stop reckless actions in time, due to excessive optimism or greed.

The purpose of the black hat is to provide an alternative, a rescue plan when events enter a critical state.

Step 6

Step six is for process control. The use of the blue hat has the task of monitoring the thinking of individuals throughout the entire decision-making process. This stage allows the trainer to make observations to the group on the previous states given by the other hats and to ensure the correct use of the hats. The trainer can use the blue hat to direct the group to another type of thinking, by changing the hats. The blue hat is the one that directs the group's discussion and coordinates the whole thinking process of this method.

This stage also has the effect of a boomerang because the inconsistencies between the other hats will make it difficult to summarize the major points of the discussion, as well as to make optimal decisions.

Step 7

After completing step six, the trainer is the one who requests the end of the work session, giving his consent regarding the actions that the group must take. Depending on the approved actions, the trainer assigns the activities necessary to solve the problem, as the case may be. The usefulness of the method is distinguished by the fact that it is allowed to assign different roles (emotional, critical, optimistic, creative) without a personal involvement. These roles in the form of metaphorical hats encourage individuals to express their irrational emotions about a business, or to expose a new and seemingly strange idea. Also, the negative element, the critique, of an action is seen as a necessary moment for the development of an idea. Those who use the method are very knowledgeable about human behavior and intuitively notice individuals who react emotionally (Red Hat) objectively (White Hat), or critically (Black Hat). Hats are used as metaphors for every direction of thinking helping individuals face a variety of key situations and find solutions to problems.

Effectiveness of the Six Thinking Hats method

The effectiveness of the method allows the analysis of the problem from all points of view, focusing each time on a single aspect, while the use of other methods overlaps the analysis functions resulting in neglecting other aspects of the problem. This creative method deals with the evolution of a problem taking into account the six states of thinking. During the thinking session, an individual's domination over

group discussions is not accepted. Due to the prohibition of this aspect, the ideas, decisions, and solutions attest to the fact that they have unwavering robustness in solving problems.

Thus, the metaphor of hats is an optimal system that requires changing the register when the data is confusing, in a negative and seemingly hopeless situation, "changing the hat" may be the simplest system to find the solution. In addition, using this system quite often, it is possible to create a kind of conditioned reflex, which will make the procedure more and more effective.

Creative thinking through "Six Thinking Hats" for educational projects

In educational projects, a major important element that requires creativity exposure is the design project. Most of the time, students receive this task in the final years, after having thoroughly laid the theoretical foundations. However, these projects should be from day one and spread throughout the program to develop skills and encourage active learning. In the current situation, the educational system requires a creative approach regarding digital education that responds to global innovative initiatives in higher education. Given the current need for creative learning based on competencies and skills, the authors put into practice an educational project to involve students in the product creative area.

Because in the past during traditional brainstorming sessions, individuals tended to use sophisticated thought processes and were undecided about what outcomes must be implemented this time authors decided to apply another method that has more valences for creative development. This change occurred because the authors noted in previous implementations of other educational projects, situations in which the implementation of new ideas was not debated on all levels correctly and this issue influenced the target group that did not identify with the practicability of the last idea. These issues have emerged because new educational projects based on digitalization involve many more factors and opportunities in digital systems that are not properly mastered by all students. Thus, during the educational process, different emotional problems are generated, perceived by the students on distinct levels. Any digitized process is instrumented by programs with different menus, functions and commands. This generates the need for digital skills combined with the necessary knowledge of the study process in the digitized system. Many students do not have this combined knowledge at the same level so in the case of creative teamwork emotions or frustrations can be generated due to these differences in knowledge and skills.

To avoid this, the research team proposed another approach that would bring new innovative proposals and arouse the interest of the target group. Thus, the use of the "Six Thinking Hats" method was taken into account.

Before starting the creative process, the students attended a workshop for the creative design process by specialists. By using the method, indications were suggested that everyone in the project should think about the same issues at the same time. Then each problem was going through the filter/hat for each way of the thinking method. A particular type of thought process was applied for problem-solving.

As was mentioned above we considered appropriate for creative process teaching and practice, the application of the "Six Thinking Hats" method for students, considering the period from March 2020, the moment of entering the state of emergency due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Thus, after declaring the state of emergency, the Politehnica University of Timisoara made available to teachers and students the virtual campus for academic year continuation.

Table 2. Hat Sequence

Brainstorm and Analyze Ideas activities	Hat sequence
Initial Ideas	White, Red , Green, Blue
Quick Feedback	Black, Red , Green, Blue
Identifying Solutions	White, Red , Black, Green, Blue
Problem-Solving	White, Red , Green, Yellow, Black, Blue
Choosing between alternatives	Green, Yellow, Black, Red , Blue
Process Improvement	White, Yellow, Black, Green, Red , Blue
Strategic Planning	Blue, Red , Yellow, Black, White, Blue, Green, Blue
Performance Review	Red , White, Yellow, Black, Green, Blue

Within the Politehnica University of Timisoara, in certain curricular materials, there were difficulties regarding the examination procedure with the students on the university virtual campus. The examination procedure had several variants were topics given to the students had on the virtual campus a limited term for uploading the studied materials / projects "Cute-off data" as well as combined evaluation topics. Specifically, in certain curricular materials, teachers who knew how to use the virtual campus interacted with students to choose between different work options for their optimal examination.

For the examination of the students, four variants were presented as follows:

- bibliographic researches to be studied in which the students had as evaluation method a quiz with limited time.
- depending on the material taught at the online course, the students had to solve a questionnaire with limited response time.
- a real-time solution in which students received a limited amount of time to give the correct answer and to upload pictures of how to solve the problem.
- combinations from quiz-questionnaire-application in different proportions and variants from such combinations depending on digitization skills and emotions.

By using the application of the "Six Thinking Hats" method students were involved in *Problem-Solving* (White, Red, Green, Yellow, Black, Blue), namely:

- White: the teacher established work options and work instructions for the examination.
- Red: the teacher received emotional responses regarding the presentation of the examination variants.
- Green: the students propose combinations of examination variants and the teacher formulates the variants also from an emotional point of view, details that he obtained through the red hat -
- Yellow: the three optimal examination options were selected, which offer opportunities for all students enrolled in the exam to obtain a passing grade.
- Black: the most extensive and complicated examination variant was identified.
- Blue: took over the simple check-list algorithms so that all the information in the other hats was processed.

Discussion and conclusions

More than ever, students must approach creative problem-solving in collaboration with stakeholder groups (actors, participants, customers, and users) to address problematic situations through collective creative thinking based on technology. Therefore, there is a great need to teach students to identify creative deepening methods and techniques that will help them solve problems. These creative approaches will bring an advantage by completing the traditional understanding in solving problems and developing an extremely rational and programmed process.

The method helped to make creative educational decisions, obtaining combinations of the four explicit methods to help students.

It also helped to find the best examination solution for a series of 120 students and for them to be involved in the learning process through digitized methods. Following the results obtained after the examination, the feedback was 85 percent positive regarding the completion of the subject. In other words, it is relevant that educators have an optimal collaboration with students in framing their competencies that need and vital for the involvement and highlighting of the labor market. This collaboration is especially important because it encourages students to improve their transferable skills and employability. Students must be prepared to generate innovative ideas through appropriate experiences, such as undertaking complex projects, working in interdisciplinary teams.

Modern challenges and global issues that demand the most attention from the current group of students will not be solved by any discipline but through teams from all disciplines, who gather their skills and expertise to create innovative solutions.

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